

Design of Low Power Modified Priority Encoder using 32-bit integer Division Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

In this project, an algorithm for 32-bit integer division is proposed. The algorithm calculates the integer division of positive and negative dividends and divisors represented in sign and magnitude. It calculates the magnitudes and signs of the quotient and remainder separately based on the magnitudes and signs of the divided and divisor. In this paper we also propose a mux based subtractor which will decrease the area by establishing a trade-off between the area & delay. In the algorithm, the magnitude of the remainder is initially set to be the dividend and is iteratively reduced until it becomes smaller than the magnitude of the divisor; afterwards the algorithm converges. A priority encoder is used to improve the convergence rate by skipping the zeros between the high bits while shifting the divisor in each iteration to be aligned with the partial remainder. The magnitude of the quotient is initially set to zero and updated based on the amount of shift in each iteration. A hardware architecture is proposed to implement the algorithm. The hardware is synthesized and simulated using Xilinx ISE 14.7.

KEYWORDS: Priority Encoder, Multiplexer, integer division, hardware implementation

1. INTRODUCTION

Integer division often refers to two closely related concepts: the actual division and the modulus. Given an integer numerator n and a nonzero integer divisor d , the integer division, written div , gives the integer quotient ($n \text{ div } d = q$). The modulus, written mod , gives the integer remainder ($n \text{ mod } d = r$). Given an integer numerator n and an integer divisor d , the quotient (q) and the remainder (r) are always integers even when the

fraction n/d is not an integer. It always holds that the quotient multiplied by the divisor plus the remainder gives back the numerator: $n = q * d + r$. Depending on the context, "integer division" might refer solely to the computation of the quotient, but might also refer to the computation of both the integer quotient and the remainder. The integer division instructions on x64 processors compute both the quotient and the remainder. In most programming languages, they are

distinct operations: the C programming language uses / for division (div) and % for modulo (mod).

Floating-point based algorithms are commonly implemented as software and executed in microprocessors. Typically, this solution requires to pay a performance penalty given that the conventional approaches require to perform the data transfer between the ALU and the program memory and the instruction memories. This problem, well known as von Neumann bottleneck, has been partially overcome by using multicore microprocessors reducing the execution time.

Recently, Graphic Processor Units (GPUs) are being widely used to implement complex algorithm taking advantage of parallel floating-point arithmetic operators, increasing the throughput and achieving an expressive speed-up. Although GPUs work with a high frequency and improve the performance, it is a microprocessor-based solution and as a consequence suffers of the von Neumann bottleneck when all the source data are accessed from global memory or when simultaneous accesses from different threads to memory have to be addressed. Additionally, GPUs commonly operate at high frequencies increasing the power consumption of the overall system, being a drawback for embedded system applications. Modern FPGAs are a suitable solution that provides hundreds of thousands of logic elements and dedicated DSP blocks as well as several desired properties such as intrinsic parallelism, flexibility, low cost and customizable approaches. All this allows for a better performance and accelerated execution of the involved algorithms on mobile applications.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The fundamentals of the QCA nanotechnology, digital comparator circuit, and existing related works are presented in Section 2. The proposed QCA-based comparator circuit is detailed in Section 3. Section 4 presents the simulation results and comparison evaluation.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Digit-recurrence algorithms are widely used in actual microprocessors to compute floating-point division and square root. These iterative algorithms present a good trade-off in terms of performance, area and power. We present a floating-point division and square root unit, which implements a radix-64 floating-point division and

a radix-16 floating-point square root. To have an affordable implementation, each radix-64 division iteration and radix-16 square root iteration are made of simpler radix-4 iterations: 3 radix-4 iterations in division and 2 in square root. Speculation is used between consecutive radix-4 iterations to get a reduced timing. There are three different parts in digit-recurrence implementations: initialization, digit iterations, and rounding. The digit iteration is the iterative part and it uses the same logic for several cycles. Division and square root share partially the initialization and rounding stages, whereas each one has different logic for the digit iterations. The result is a low-latency floating-point divider and square root, requiring 11, 6, and 4 cycles for double, single and half-precision division with normalized operands and result, and 15, 8 and 5 cycles for square root. One or two additional cycles are needed in case of subnormal operand(s) or result. The two floating-point operations being performed in this unit are division and square root. The result is precision and half-precision division, and 15, 8 and 5 cycles for double precision, single precision and half-precision square a low latency floating-point digit-recurrence 11 divider and square root unit, with latencies of 11, 6 and 4 cycles for double-precision, single root.

Integer division, i.e., division of two integers yielding an integer quotient and an integer remainder, is one of the basic arithmetic operations. In modern micro-processors, integer division takes many clock cycles, even more than double precision floating-point division. Furthermore, the number of clock cycles for integer division varies depending on the operands' values. In this paper, we propose a new hardware algorithm for integer division and discuss integer dividers based on the algorithm. The algorithm is based on the digit-recurrence, non-restoring division algorithm. In order to accelerate digit recurrence division by dedicated hardware, it is quite natural to employ carry save or signed-digit representation for representing partial remainders and to perform addition/subtractions without carry/borrow propagation. However, to do so, we have to normalize the divisor, and hence, require an area consuming 12 leading one (or zero) detector and a barrel shifter. Actually, Wang et al. recently proposed such integer

dividers. The number of clock cycles by these integer dividers varies depending on the operands' values.

The most popular methods for the speed-up of the division operation are the modifications of the traditional restoring and non-restoring algorithms. Among these modifications, the SRT algorithm is the most widely used. The main idea of this method is to use limited comparisons to speed-up the selection of the quotient. Typically, the hardware implementations of the different forms of the SRT algorithm present the lowest area requirements but, at the same time, the high latency is a drawback of these designs. A lot of computational tasks implemented in programmable logic use the fixed-point division operation, whose preciseness often has to be extended. The standard IP Core "Pipelined Divider" from Xilinx has a limitation – the widths of the operands and precision of the result can be at most 32 bits. The detailed study of different division algorithms has shown the advantages of the implementation of the non-restoring algorithm versus other ones. Moreover, our design is completely parameterized and there are no restrictions for the widths of the input operands and the result of division. For the 32-bit wide dividend, divider, quotient and remainder the division module with non-restoring algorithm has the clock frequency 245 MHz vs. 193 MHz of IP Core from Xilinx on Virtex-II Pro FPGA. Our fixed-point division modules were tested for the large widths of input operands, e.g. 64-and 128-bit, and for the different precision values of the result.

3. PROPOSED WORK:

In the existing method, a Booth-like modulo algorithm is proposed. A hardware architecture that implements the proposed algorithm is also suggested. The proposed algorithm can calculate modulo of positive and negative numbers in a varying number of clock cycles that is always less than or equal to the number of clock cycles used by traditional techniques such as binary dividers. Modulo operator is heavily used in coding techniques such as encryption and channel coding. For example, the Rivest Shamir Aldeman (RSA) scheme of encryption finds modulo between the message raised to an exponent and a prime number. This operation is done through an algorithm called fast exponentiation that heavily utilizes modulo operator. Also, Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) techniques use modulo operator to

create prime finite fields RSI similarly, channel coding techniques such as Reed-Solomon coding r61 are based on Galois finite fields that are based on modulo operations. A major distinction between channel coding techniques and encryption techniques lies in how the modulo operator is used: in channel coding, modulo operation is done on relatively small integers, whereas for encryption, modulo operator is performed on integers with thousands or millions of decimal digits.

In this proposed algorithm, k is an index that keeps track of the clock cycles, start is a control input that is set to high for one clock cycle at the beginning of computation, x and n are the two data inputs, out is the data output and done is an output flag that changes to high when the output is correct. In addition, o, p, q and f are temporary variables used to iterate the current sum/difference. The number of steps needed to compute the mod operation depends on the value of the inputs. Hence, the proposed algorithm is similar to Booth multiplication. This algorithm can be easily transferred to hardware.

The block diagram of the proposed architecture is shown in Figure

Fig: The proposed architecture for the modulo operator

It has a clock clk, two data inputs x and n, one control input start, one data output out, and one 20 flag output done. It consists of three multiplexers, one subtractor, two adders/subtractors, three registers, three priority encoders and one barrel shifter. The first multiplexer (mux1) has an output o and is used to select between the registered feedback signal f and the input x. The second multiplexer (mux2) is used to select between the outputs of the two different types of priority encoders. The third multiplexer mux3 is used to select between the outputs

of the two adders/subtractors. The first register (reg1) is used to register o and generate the output out. The second register (reg2) is used to register the done flag. The third register (reg3) is used to register the feedback signal. All registers are reset by a high start. The first priority encoder (enc1) is a type I encoder and is used to find floor ($\log_2(o) + 1$ for $o \geq 0$). The second priority encoder (enc2) is a type 2 encoder and is used to find ceil ($\log_2(\text{modulus } o) + 1$ for $o < 0$). The third priority encoder (enc3) is a type 1 encoder and is used to find floor ($\log_2(n) + 1$).

The barrel shifter shifts n by both a and a-1 to generate na and na-1, respectively, where $na = na-1 = n$ for $a \leq 0$. The first adder/subtractor is used to compute $p = o \pm na$. It should be noted here that as long as $a > 0$, the low significant bits of p are equal to the low significant bits of o. Hence this computation is only necessary for the most significant floor ($\log_2(n)$) bits of p. It should be noted here that as long as $a > 0$, the low significant bits of p are equal to the low significant bits of o. Hence this computation is only necessary for the most significant floor ($\log_2(n)$) bits of p. The second adder/subtractor is used to compute $q = o \pm na-1$. Similarly, this computation is only necessary for the most significant floor ($\log_2(n) + 1$) bits of q.

The feedback signal f is equal to either p or q depending on the control signal ctrl, where $ctrl = \sim msbo \& (\sim msbp) + msbo (\sim msbq)$. Finally, an AND gate calculates the done flag, where $done = msbpbmsbq$. Table III is a truth table showing the relation between the control, done and feedback signals and the most significant bits of o, p and q.

4 SIMULATION RESULTS:

Fig: RTL Schematic of Priority encoder

Fig: Technological Schematic of Priority encoder

Fig: Simulation waveforms of Priority encoder

Design	Area(LUT's)	Delay(ns)
Existing[4]	4172	102.5
Existing[3]	2704	74.6
Existing[5]	1152	85
Existing[2]	774	43
Existing(Full subtractors based on XOR & AND gates)	631	35.388
Proposed(Full subtractors based on MUX)	621	32.066

Table: Comparison Table

Graphical Representation

5. CONCLUSION:

This paper proposes a 32-bit integer division algorithm that is based on priority encoder. The algorithm performs division on numbers represented in sign and magnitude, and produces a quotient and remainder that are also represented in sign and magnitude. Due to the utilization of the priority encoder, the algorithm converges fast by skipping zeros in the quotient and focusing only on the high bits. Also, the algorithm does not require the number of bits of the dividend and divisor as an input, and can work for any bit length that is less than or equal to 32. A hardware architecture is proposed to implement the algorithm. In this project we replaced the conventional full subtractors which are implemented with "xor" & "and" logic gates with a full subtractor designed using multiplexers. Such that area can be reduced with a trade-off between delay.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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